

Client Satisfaction with In-Patient Care and its Relationship with the First Out-Patient Follow-up Visit in Persons with Schizophrenia: A Longitudinal Design

Chinyere Mirian Aguocha, Emeka Chinwuba Nwefoh

ABSTRACT

Background: Missed appointment has been recognized as a major problem in the management of persons with mental illness. **Objectives:** The objective of this study was to assess client satisfaction with in-patient care and its relationship with the first out-patient follow-up visit in persons with schizophrenia. **Methods:** A longitudinal study of 311 in-patients with a diagnosis of schizophrenia. Diagnosis of schizophrenia was confirmed using the Munich version of the Composite International Diagnostic Interview. Socio-demographic data were collected using a structured questionnaire. The client Satisfaction Questionnaire (CSQ-8) was used to measure patient satisfaction. **Results:** Increasing total CSQ-8 score was significantly associated with a decrease in the likelihood of missing the first post-hospitalization appointment (AOR: 0.71; 95% CI 0.64-0.79, $p < 0.05$). **Conclusion:** Discharged patients who were satisfied with the care received during admission are more likely to turn up for post-hospitalization care.

Keywords: Client satisfaction, schizophrenia, treatment, developing country

INTRODUCTION

A missed appointment is the failure of a person to appear for a scheduled clinic appointment without notification.¹ This has been recognized as a common problem in the management of persons with mental illness.^{2,3} Missed appointment adversely affects patient outcome, with an increased rate of premature mortality and a greater rate of readmission.^{4,5} Patients are most likely to drop out of care during the early stages of treatment, especially during the period of transition from in-patient to out-patient care.^{6,7}

Client satisfaction is one of the performance indicators used for assessing service efficiency and health outcomes.⁸ The purpose of measuring client satisfaction is to determine the client's perception of the quality of care and

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Affiliation:

Department of Internal Medicine, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria.

*Correspondence:

Aguocha Chinyere Mirian. Department of Medicine, Imo State University, Owerri

Email: aguochainvest@yahoo.com

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to utilize this to enhance service delivery.⁸ Satisfied patients have been reported as more likely to comply with treatment, keep follow-up appointments, and utilize health services.⁹ Unfortunately in Nigeria, mental health hospital administrators place a low emphasis on routine or regular client satisfaction surveys as a means of auditing hospital performance and service delivery. This has led to difficulties in identifying factors that lead to poor utilization of services.

Some of the factors identified to affect client satisfaction include quality of therapeutic interventions, quality of staff interaction with patients, confidentiality, information on disease and medication, adjustment of the program to patient expectations, clinic organization, and environment.¹⁰ A welcoming, well-decorated, clean and orderly environment encourages patients to return for appointments.¹¹

The level of satisfaction with mental health care in Nigeria and Africa is generally poorer than what is reported globally.^{12, 13, 14} Studies carried out in Nigeria have shown a fair to good level of satisfaction with out-patient care.^{14, 15 16} The level of satisfaction was found to be greater among male patients aged less than 40 years.¹⁵ The greatest areas of dissatisfaction were in the high cost of treatment, insufficient provision of information, insufficient time spent with patients, and lack of privacy and services while the greatest areas of satisfaction were in the areas of staff-patient interaction and the quality of medical care provided.^{14, 15, 16}

Most of the studies carried out on client satisfaction in Nigeria have been focused on out-patient services with little or no study on satisfaction with in-patient care.

The objective of the study was to assess client satisfaction with in-patient care and its relationship with the attendance of the first post-hospitalization appointment among persons with schizophrenia in a developing country. It was hypothesized that greater satisfaction with in-patient care would be associated with a greater turn-up rate for the first post-hospitalization appointment. It is hoped that this study would encourage more studies on the identification of

factors that would increase the retention of patients in care post-hospitalization.

METHODS

Study respondents

This was a prospective observational study carried out at the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Enugu. The hospital is a Federal Government funded tertiary health institution which provides services mainly to inhabitants of the South East Geopolitical zone and its environs. The hospital receives referrals from all the South Eastern states of Nigeria, as well as from nearby zones. On average, the hospital provides services to about 1550 patients monthly, out of whom about 10 percent are new patients. New and defaulting patients are attended to at the emergency and crisis intervention unit of the hospital. Those who cannot be cared for on an out-patient basis are transferred to the in-patient wards.

The study population consisted of new patients with a diagnosis of schizophrenia confirmed with the Munich version of the Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI), aged between 18 and 64 years, admitted into the hospital during the period of study, who were physically and mentally able to participate and who consented to participate in the study.

Study population and sampling method

Sample size was determined using the Cochran formula¹⁷; $n = z^2qp/d^2$, where n = sample size, p = prevalence and $q=1-p$. The prevalence 'p' was from a previous Nigerian study which reported a non-attendance rate of 27.4%.¹⁸ The calculated sample size was 305.7 and taking into consideration 10% attrition, the approximate compensated sample size of 340 was calculated.

Instruments

Structured questionnaire

This was used to obtain basic information about the respondents. On admission, information obtained included the respondent's age, gender, marital status, religious affiliation, employment status, level of

education, history of mental illness, and previous admissions. The approximate distance that the patient traveled from his usual place of abode to the hospital, cost of treatment, duration of admission, and duration from discharge to first clinic appointment were also documented.

Client Satisfaction Questionnaire (CSQ-8).

The client satisfaction questionnaire was developed by Clifford Attkisson and Daniel L. Larsen to measure satisfaction with health services.¹⁹ It is an 8-item, easily scored, and administered instrument. The CSQ-8 can be used reliably in all ethnic groups.²⁰ Scores are summed across items. Items 2, 4, 5, and 8 are reverse scored. Total scores range from eight to 32, with the highest number indicating the greatest satisfaction. The CSQ-8 is copy-righted. Appropriate copyright permission was obtained from the authors. This instrument was interviewer-administered at discharge.

The majority of the inhabitants in the location of the study speak Igbo language fluently. A team of language experts at the Department of Linguistics, Igbo, and other Nigerian Languages at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka translated all the research instruments used for the study into Igbo language. The iterative method was adopted. First, the instrument was translated from English to Igbo. The second group of the team then back-translated the Igbo version to English. The two teams met to reconcile any differences, producing a consensus version of the instruments. The translators provided the author with the Igbo software font. E.N clarified technical terms during the translation. Copies of the questionnaires were administered to 15 patients who were fluent in both English and Igbo languages. Both the English and Igbo versions of the questionnaires were administered and showed good similarity when responses were compared.

The instruments were administered by EN who is a psychiatrist.

Procedure

All new patients with a diagnosis of schizophrenia admitted into the wards were approached within the

first week of admission for consent and recruitment into the study. Diagnosis of Schizophrenia made by the attending psychiatrist using ICD 10 was confirmed using M-CIDI. Thereafter, the structured questionnaire was administered by E.N who maintained contact with the doctors in the respondents' managing units to ascertain when they were due to be discharged from the ward. On the day of the respondent's discharge, E.N administered the CSQ-8. The appointment dates were also recorded.

On the date of the first appointment, all the records of patients seen on that day were examined to determine the respondents who kept their appointment. Out-patient services were provided by the same inpatient provider. Data collection lasted for 8 months.

Ethical issues

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Federal Neuropsychiatric Hospital, Enugu. Written informed consent was obtained. It was clearly stated that the refusal of a patient to participate or continue in the study at any point would not affect the quality of care received from the hospital. All data were treated with confidentiality and anonymity was maintained.

Data analysis

The personal computer (PC) version of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 21 (SPSS 21) was used for the statistical analysis.²¹ First post-hospitalization visit was defined as a visit to the hospital on the date of the first scheduled out-patient appointment following discharge from the hospital. Respondents were grouped into those who kept the first out-patient appointment and those who did not. The cost of transportation was converted from naira to dollars.

Approximate distance in kilometers (km) in which respondents traveled from their usual place of abode to the hospital was re-coded into short (<10km), medium (10-20km), and long (>20km).²² Using quartile values (25th, 50th, and 75th), the travel time was re-coded to short (7-20 minutes), medium (21-50 minutes) and long (>50 minutes); the cost of transportation into low (0.13-0.53 dollars), medium

(0.54-1.52dollars) and high (>1.52dollars) while the duration of admission was re-coded into short (<5 weeks), medium (6-7 weeks) and long (>7 weeks). The period from discharge to the first appointment was re-coded into short (<3weeks) and long (≥ 3 weeks) because of a similar value of 2 weeks for both the 25th and 50th quartile.²³

The variables that were significantly associated with appointment keeping (based on CSQ-8 scores) were then entered into a logistic regression analysis to determine the predictors of appointment keeping. Appointment keeping was entered as the dependent variable while gender, marital status, history of mental illness, usual living arrangement, and highest level of education were entered as factors. CSQ total, duration of hospital admission, duration from discharge to follow-up, distance, travel time, and cost of transportation from the place of abode, were entered as covariates.

Results were calculated as frequencies, means, and standard deviations. Analysis of Variance and t-tests were used to determine the differences in mean CSQ scores among those who kept and those who did not keep their hospital appointments. A significant level was computed at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Nine hundred and sixty-four patients were admitted to the hospital during the study period. Three hundred and forty patients met the inclusion criteria and were recruited into the study. No patient refused consent. Twenty-nine out of the 340 respondents recruited for the study had incomplete data, leaving a sample size of 311 for analysis. One hundred and seventy-one (55%) of the respondents were female. The males were aged 32.5 ± 10.83 years while the females were aged 35.84 ± 10.98 years. One hundred and eighty-five (59.5%) of the respondents were single and 126 (40.5%) were married. Two hundred and ninety respondents (93.2%) were Christians. More of those who failed to keep their first post-hospitalisation appointment were males, 45 (32.1%), those who were not married, 59 (31.9%), and those who lived alone, 21 (48.8%).

Table 1 shows a summary of the mean CSQ scores of

the respondents. The result showed varying levels of satisfaction with care. Two hundred and sixty (83.6%) rated the services as excellent or good. A majority, 252 (61%) got the services they wanted. Most, 202 (65%) indicated that the services provided met most or almost all their needs. A majority, 274 (88.1%) would recommend the services to a friend in need of similar help. Most, 229 (73.6%) were very satisfied or mostly satisfied with the amount of help received. Most of the respondents, 239 (76.8%) indicated that the services had helped them somewhat and a great deal in dealing with their problems. A majority, 234 (75.2%) were in an overall sense, very satisfied, and mostly satisfied with the services received. Two hundred and forty respondents (77.2%) indicated that they would return to the center if there was a need to seek help again.

Table 2 shows the association between the mean CSQ scores with socio-demographic variables. Female respondents ($t = -5.2$, $p < 0.001$), the married ($t = -3.0$, $p = 0.003$), those who lived with their family ($F = 7.4$, $p < 0.001$), and those with greater than six years of education ($F = 1.50$, $p = 0.007$) had significantly higher mean CSQ scores. Those who traveled 10-20km from their usual abode to the hospital ($F = 4.92$, $p < 0.008$), whose travel time to the hospital was 21-50 minutes ($F = 17.72$, $p < 0.001$), whose time from discharge to follow-up was <3 weeks ($t = 9.06$, $p < 0.001$), and whose cost of transportation was 0.54-1.5 dollars ($F = 13.71$, $p < 0.001$) reported significantly higher mean CSQ scores.

Pair-wise comparisons of the means using Tukey HSD revealed significant differences in satisfaction between those who lived alone and those who lived with their family; those who traveled 10-20km from their usual abode to the hospital and those who traveled greater than 20km; those whose travel time was greater than 50 minutes and other subsets and those whose transportation cost was above 1.5 dollars and other subsets ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3 shows the association between socio-demographic characteristics, appointment keeping, and the mean CSQ scores of the respondents. A higher mean CSQ score (26.9 ± 3.4) was significantly associated with first appointment keeping ($t = 18.82$, $p < 0.001$). Females ($F = 27.5$, $p = 0.00$), married ($F = 9.6$,

$p < 0.001$), those who lived with their families ($F=7.6$, $p < 0.001$), those with more than six years of education, ($F=2.9$, $p=0.04$) and those who had a past history of mental illness ($F=5.6$, $p=0.02$) had significantly higher mean CSQ scores and these were significantly associated with keeping their first post-hospitalization appointment. Also, those who traveled a long distance to the hospital ($F=343.15$, $p < 0.001$), those with a medium travel time of 21-50 minutes ($F=343.15$, $p < 0.001$), those with a low cost of treatment ($F=343.15$, $p < 0.001$), those whose duration of hospital admission was long ($F=299.04$, $p < 0.001$), and whose duration from discharge to follow up was short ($F=343.15$, $p < 0.001$), had significantly higher mean CSQ scores, which was associated with keeping the first post-hospitalization appointment.

Table 4 shows the determinants of appointment keeping. The logistic regression model was statistically significant, $\chi^2 (14) = 240.49$, $p < 0.001$. The model explained 79.2% (Nagelkerke R^2) of the variance in appointment keeping. Males were about four times more likely to keep their first post-hospitalization appointment compared with females, (AOR: 3.93; 95% CI 1.25-12.31, $p < 0.05$).

Increasing total CSQ score was associated with an increase in the likelihood of keeping first post-hospitalization appointment (AOR: 1.46; 95% CI 1.30-1.64, $p < 0.05$). An increasing duration from discharge to follow-up was associated with a decrease in the likelihood of keeping the first post-hospitalization appointment (AOR: 0.61; CI 0.47-0.80, $p < 0.05$). Those who had no form of formal education were significantly less likely to keep their first appointment (AOR: 0.14; 95% CI 0.02-0.80, $p < 0.05$). It was also found that the higher the level of education, the higher the likelihood of appointment keeping.

Table 1: Summary of measures of client satisfaction

Variable	n	%
Q1. How do you rate the quality of service you received?		
Excellent	117	37.5
Good	143	45.8
Fair	35	11.2
Poor	16	5.1
Q2. Did you get the kind of service you wanted?		
No, definitely not	20	6.4
No, not really	39	12.5
Yes, generally	173	55.4
Yes, definitely	79	25.3
Q3. To what extent did our health services meet your needs?		
Almost all my needs have been met	23	7.4
Most of my needs have been met	179	57.4
Only few of my needs have been met	95	30.4
None of my needs have been met	14	4.5
Q4. If a friend were in need of similar help, would you recommend our service to him or her?		
No, definitely not	11	3.5
No, not really	26	8.3
Yes, generally	121	38.8
Yes, definitely	153	49.0
Q5. How satisfied are you with the amount of help you have received?		
Quite dissatisfied	41	13.1
Indifferent, or mildly satisfied	41	13.1
Mostly satisfied	138	44.2
Very satisfied	91	29.2
Q6. Have the services you received helped you to deal more effectively with your problems?		
No, they seemed to make things worse	13	4.2
No, they really did not help	59	18.9
Yes, they have helped somewhat	126	40.4
Yes, they have helped a great deal	113	36.2
Q7. In an overall, general sense, how satisfied are you with the service you have received?		
Quite dissatisfied	44	14.1
Indifferent, or mildly satisfied	33	10.6
Mostly satisfied	129	41.3
Very satisfied	105	33.7
Q8. If you were to seek help again, would you come back to our hospital?		
No, definitely not	12	3.8
No, I don't think so	59	18.9
Yes, I think so	82	26.3
Yes, definitely	158	50.6

Table 2: Association between socio-demographic characteristics and Client satisfaction

Variables	CSQ score Mean (S.D)	Stat	P value
Gender			
Male	22.5(6.2)		
Female	25.9(5.1)	t=-5.2	p< 0.001 *
Current marital status			
Single†	23.5(6.3)		
Married	25.9(4.9)	t=-3.03	p=0.003*
Religion			
Christianity	24.49±5.90		
Others	22.62±5.24	t=1.41	p=0.16
Usual living arrangement			
Lives alone	21.8(6.7)		
With family	25.1(5.5)		
With others	22.7(6.3)	F=7.4	p< 0.001 *
Highest level of education			
Less than 6 years of education	22.58(6.21)		
More than 6 years of education	24.82(5.70)	t=1.5	p=0.007*
Employment status			
Employed	23.7±6.1		
Unemployed	25.0±5.6	t=1.9	p=0.06
History of mental illness			
Yes	25.6(4.8)		
No	23.9(6.2)	t=2.4	p=0.02*
Previous admission for Mental illness			
Yes	23.5(6.1)		
No	24.5(5.9)	t=-0.9	p=0.4
Family History of mental illness			
Yes	24.7(5.8)		
No	24.2(5.9)	t=0.7	p=0.46
Distance traveled			
Short	24.7±5.15		
Medium	26.14±3.56		
Long	23.67±6.52	F=4.92	p=0.008*
Travel time			
Short	25.76±4.06		
Medium	26.64±4.01		
Long	22.42±6.89	F=17.72	p<0.001*
Cost of transportation			
Low	25.54±4.41		
Medium	26.57±3.86		
High	22.72±6.82	F=13.71	p<0.001*
Duration of admission			
Short	24.18±6.13		
Medium	25.02±5.22		
Long	24.07±6.10	F=0.41	p=0.62
Duration from discharge to follow up			
Short	26.79±4.00		
Long	21.40±6.42	t=9.06	p<0.001*

†never married, separated, divorced or widowed *significant F=ANOVA

Table 3: Association between socio-demographic characteristics, appointment keeping and CSQ

Variables	CSQ scores		stat	p-value
	Appointment kept			
	Yes Mean(SD)	No Mean(SD)		
Total CSQ scores	26.9(3.4)	17.2(5.4)	t=18.82	< 0.001*
Gender				
Male	25.6(3.6)	16.1(5.8)	t=27.5	< 0.001*
Female	27.8(3.0)	18.5(4.7)		
Current marital status				
Single	26.8(3.6)	16.5(5.0)	t=9.6	< 0.001*
Married	26.9(3.3)	19.0(6.2)		
Religion				
Christianity	26.94(3.44)	16.87(5.47)	t=2.04	0.16
Others	25.73(3.26)	19.20(4.94)		
Usual living arrangement				
Lives alone	26.6(4.40)	16.8(4.9)	t=343.15	< 0.001*
With others	26.9 (3.3)	17.3(5.7)		
Highest level of education				
Less than 6 years of education	26.74 (2.69)	17.33 (5.35)	t=343.15	< 0.001*
More than 6 years of education	26.90 (3.44)	17.08 (5.52)		
Employment status				
Employed	27.1(3.3)	17.2(5.3)	t=3.3	0.70
Unemployed	26.5(3.6)	17.1(5.6)		
Patient History of mental illness				
Yes	27.2 (3.2)	20.0(5.3)	t=5.6	0.02*
No	26.8(3.6)	16.12(5.2)		
Previous admission for mental illness				
Yes	25.4(5.2)	27.0(3.2)	t=0.8	0.40
No	20.1(6.1)	16.7(5.2)		
Family History of mental illness				
Yes	26.9 (3.5)	26.9 (3.4)	t=0.5	0.50
No	16.8 (5.7)	17.3 (5.3)		
Distance traveled				
Short	26.20 (3.75)	20.20 (3.75)	F=343.15	< 0.001*
Medium	26.52 (3.26)	19.50 (1.29)		
Long	27.22 (3.44)	16.56 (5.32)		
Travel time				
Short	26.41 (3.45)	20.82 (5.02)	F=343.15	< 0.001*
Medium	27.38 (2.76)	20.00 (6.98)		
Long	26.96 (3.84)	16.19 (5.00)		
Cost of transportation				
Low	26.44 (3.51)	19.75 (5.34)	F=343.15	< 0.001*
Medium	27.11 (2.72)	19.80 (8.53)		
High	26.88 (3.43)	16.46 (5.05)		
Duration of admission				
Short	26.70 (3.82)	16.36 (5.33)	F=299.04	< 0.001*
Medium	26.82 (3.15)	17.64 (5.61)		
Long	27.14 (3.26)	16.92 (5.13)		
Duration from discharge to follow up				
Short	27.16 (3.30)	18.14 (8.17)	F=343.15	< 0.001*
Long	26.18 (3.70)	21.40 (6.42)		

* = significant F=ANOVA t= t test

Table 4: Determinants of appointment keeping

	B	S.E	AOR	95% C.I	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Distance traveled to hospital (km)	0.001	0.01	1.001	0.98	1.03
Travel time (minutes)	-0.008	0.01	0.99	0.97	1.02
Cost of transportation	-0.001	0.002	1.00	1.00	1.00
CSQ total	0.38	0.06	1.46*	1.30	1.64
Duration from discharge to follow up (weeks)	-1.77	0.45	0.17*	0.07	0.41
Gender					
Male ^a	1.37	0.58	3.93*	1.25	12.31
Marital status					
Single ^b	-0.33	0.64	0.72	0.20	2.52
History of mental illness					
Yes ^c	-0.44	0.61	0.65	0.20	2.14
Usual living arrangement					
Alone ^d	0.14	1.84	1.15	0.03	42.14
Family	0.55	1.79	1.73	0.05	57.78
Friends	-0.15	1.91	0.86	0.02	36.51
Highest level of education					
None ^e	-2.00	0.91	0.14*	0.02	0.80
Primary	0.52	0.84	1.68	0.32	8.79
Secondary	1.23	0.69	3.43	0.89	13.19

*significant

^aReference category: females^bReference category: married^cReference category: no^dReference category: others^eReference category: tertiary

DISCUSSION

This study measured and assessed client satisfaction with in-patient treatment and its association with attendance of first post-discharge clinic appointment among recently discharged persons with schizophrenia. There were four major findings.

Firstly, greater client satisfaction was associated with an increased likelihood of attendance of first post-discharge clinic appointments. This is similar to what has been previously reported.²⁴ Intuitively, this is expected since the termination of appointments might be assumed to represent a behavioral sign of dissatisfaction. This hunch is confirmed by our result showing that those who missed their appointments had lower satisfaction scores.

Secondly, an increasing duration from discharge to follow-up was associated with a decreased level of satisfaction and an increase in the likelihood of missed first post-discharge clinic appointment. This is similar to reports of long appointment waiting time being a major source of dissatisfaction for patients and their relatives.²⁵ The patients and their relatives lose interest

in the treatment because of the belief that the patient no longer needs further treatment since the patient to them has apparently recovered. These factors are heightened because of the factors peculiar to developing countries such as an insufficient number of health care workers to cope with the large influx of patients at the out-patient department leading to long waiting time, long distance, and travel time from the patient's place of abode to the hospital. These problems could be tackled by engaging more specialists to run the out-patient clinics and training health workers in primary health care centers (PHCs) on the identification and management of common mental disorders. These workers could continue the management of these patients in the PHCs post-discharge. Also patient and caregiver convenience must be taken into consideration during appointment scheduling.

Thirdly, we found that females expressed a greater level of satisfaction with care which could explain

their being better at keeping their first out-patient appointment. However, there are varying reports on the effect of gender on client satisfaction. One study found greater satisfaction among male patients while yet another found higher satisfaction in females.^{10, 26} Another reported no difference in satisfaction between males and females regarding physician care.²⁷ The varying reports could be attributed to differences in culture, attitude towards assessing care, and expectations from service providers. Studies have reported that male patients preferred greater involvement in decision making, and personal interest shown in them by providers while female patients prefer an explanation about the cause of illness, informational content, continuity of care, and multidisciplinary treatment.^{27,28} Lastly, we found that a higher level of education was associated with a greater level of satisfaction and an increase in the likelihood of appointment keeping by the patients.

The increased satisfaction with greater education could be due to differences in health providers' attitudes towards the clients based on perceived social status. Those with greater education are more likely to be perceived to have a higher social status. Also, those with greater education have a better ability to express their needs.

The greater satisfaction found among the married and those living with their families could be due to increased social support provided by the family. The greater satisfaction experienced by these people is expected to manifest in increased appointment keeping. This is in keeping with reports by several studies that there was a positive relationship between satisfaction and appointment keeping.^{29,30,31}

Significance

Knowledge of the variables that affect appointment keeping has the potential to prepare grounds for possible interventions to reduce the rate and risk of non-attendance. Strategies targeted at improving these variables will hopefully improve appointment keeping by patients and on the whole, improve clinical outcomes.

CONCLUSION

It may be possible for clinicians to better predict attendance of first out-patient follow-up appointment following hospitalization based on the level of satisfaction with services. It is recommended that clinicians make an effort to determine their clients' expectations from treatment. Also, effort should be made to get feedback from patients about possible service barriers and administrative errors that could affect client satisfaction.

Limitations

The use of an interviewer-administered questionnaire to measure treatment satisfaction may introduce a possible response-set bias. Sample selection was not randomized, so selection bias may not be ruled out. The result from this study was drawn from a tertiary hospital, so findings may not be generalized to the primary and secondary levels. Causal implications cannot be inferred from mere associations.

Despite these caveats, the results provide useful information about important and common clinical variables responsible for missed first outpatient appointments relevant to developing countries with limited power and facilities. These may provide guide clinicians and hospital administrators in service provision.

Authors' contributions

EN wrote the proposal and protocol. EN recruited, trained, and retrained the service provider and field assistants. CA and EN analyzed the data set. CA drafted the manuscript. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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